

Proof-of-work versus proof-of-stake coins as possible hedges against green and dirty energy

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Abstract

This article examines whether high- and low-environmental impact cryptocurrencies play a role as hedging instruments for green and non-green energy instruments. We differentiate between cryptocurrencies with two types of consensus mechanisms, proof-of-work and proof-of-stake, which reflect the energy demand used for the coins' confirmation. We obtain volatilities and dynamic conditional correlations from stochastic volatility models and apply them to calculate hedge ratios. Based on the sample from 15 January 2019 to 15 September 2022, we find that clean coins provide equally good protection, measured by the hedge effectiveness, as compared to dirty coins. Yet, in each case, such effectiveness was time-varying and insignificant in some periods. Overall, cryptocurrencies are more effective hedges for oil than for clean energy assets.

1 Introduction

Cryptocurrencies, as relatively modern instruments on the financial markets, raise concerns about sustainability (Mora et al., 2018; Jones et al., 2022). These concerns are related to the energy consumption resulting from cryptocurrency confirmation mechanisms. Two general consensus mechanisms are used in cryptocurrencies: proof-of-work (PoW), also known as mining, and proof-of-stake (PoS). Due to consensus mechanisms, cryptocurrencies are divided into environmentally burdensome (dirty, PoW) or environmentally neutral (clean, PoS) (Ren and Lucey, 2022). The cryptocurrencies that use mining tremendously increase energy consumption (Yousaf et al., 2024). Digital mining creates a significant carbon footprint due to the vast amount of energy it requires, as indicated by the Cambridge Bitcoin Electricity Consumption (which captures approximate power consumption related to Bitcoin mining over time¹) or the Bitcoin Energy Consumption Index².

This paper examines the dependency between cryptocurrencies with different consensus mechanisms and energy sources, both clean and dirty. We determine whether the "clean" and "dirty" cryptocurrencies can be used as hedges against the clean energy index and crude oil. Hedges are instruments whose returns are at least temporarily negatively correlated (or at least insignificantly correlated) with the returns of the underlying assets, resulting in the possibility

¹<https://ccaf.io/cbeci/index>

²<https://digiconomist.net/bitcoin-energy-consumption>

of constructing a portfolio with a lower variance (Bouri et al., 2017; Dyhrberg et al., 2018; Dyhrberg, 2016; Baur and Lucey, 2010). Several works confirmed the safe-haven or hedge features of cryptocurrencies (Kliber et al., 2019; Umar et al., 2021; Kang et al., 2020), others rejected (Klein et al., 2018), but the environmental issues are rarely considered when examining hedging opportunities. The exception is a paper of Ren and Lucey (2022), which examines the role of clean and dirty coins as safe-haven assets against clean energy assets and vice versa. We extend that paper by exploring the possibility of the "green" and "dirty" cryptocurrencies to hedge oil price fluctuations.

Our sample period starts in January 2019 and ends in September 2022³, containing several turbulent periods. We consider ten coins, five confirmed through the proof-of-work mechanism and five through proof-of-stake. The first group includes Bitcoin, Ethereum, Bitcoin Cash, Ethereum Classic and Litecoin, and the second group includes Cardano, Ripple, IOTA, Stellar and Nano. Dirty energy is represented by Brent crude oil, and the NASDAQ CELS index approximates the clean energy sector. We apply a multivariate stochastic volatility model with dynamic conditional correlation and thus obtain the intervals of dynamic correlations. Based on that, we assess the potential for hedging and compare the strength of dependency between both types of cryptocurrencies and energy assets.

Our findings show that the difference between the hedging effectiveness of dirty and clean cryptocurrencies concerning oil is negligible. Moreover, the effectiveness of the crypto-hedge against oil is higher than the analogous hedge against green energy. The latter is insignificantly different from zero most of the time, while the effectiveness of the crypto-hedge against oil increases significantly during turbulences in the oil market.

We contribute to the existing literature in several ways. First, we focus on the instantaneous dependencies between different asset classes and the importance of the environmental aspect in portfolio construction. Specifically, we consider the hedging abilities for securing clean or dirty energy sources with clean or dirty cryptocurrencies. In similar studies, cryptocurrencies are considered either as the hedge against oil (Tarchella et al., 2024; Będowska-Sójka and Kliber, 2022; Okorie and Lin, 2020) or the clean energy sources (Ren and Lucey, 2022; Anwer et al., 2023; Arfaoui et al., 2023). In this study, we consider both energy sources jointly, and we take into account the environmental profile of cryptocurrencies.

Second, we enrich the mainstream literature usually considering dynamic conditional correlations (Tarchella et al., 2024; Kamal and Hassan, 2022; Liu et al., 2020) by applying the stochastic volatility models, which allow us to obtain the confidence intervals for correlations instead of point estimates. It offers a broader look at the hedging potential for the cryptocurrencies of both types. Third, in a methodologically similar spirit to Baur and Hoang (2021) and Just and Echaust (2024), we verify the hedging effectiveness of the constructed portfolios and analyse the hedging ability of clean and dirty cryptocurrencies to clean and dirty energy at the same time. However, our approach allows us to assess the statistical significance of the hedge effectiveness, which has been neglected in the literature so far. Finally, unlike other studies (Umar et al., 2021; Ren and Lucey, 2022), we focus only on investable assets. It applies particularly to the choice of a green energy index, CELS, which is replicated by the First Trust Nasdaq Clean Edge Green Energy Index Fund, QCLN.

2 Literature review

The literature on hedging and the safe-haven property of Bitcoin started to evolve with the concept of Digital or New Gold (Baur and Hoang, 2021; Klein et al., 2018; Selmi et al., 2022). Cryptocurrencies other than Bitcoin are less frequently studied. Jareño et al. (2021) studied

³Since the 15th of September 2022, Ether is within the transferring process from PoW to PoS

the daily returns of eleven top cryptocurrencies by market capitalisation jointly with oil price movements from November 20, 2018, to June 30, 2020. The scholars demonstrated a specific behaviour of Tether, which was the least connected to the three components of oil price returns and, therefore, could serve as a diversifier or a safe-haven. [Yin et al. \(2021\)](#) examined three cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin, Ethereum, and XRP, and six oil market shocks and found that under specific uncertain economic conditions, these cryptocurrencies could act as hedges. [Anwer et al. \(2023\)](#) concentrated on the dynamic dependency of digital assets and green assets. They found that environmentally sustainable indices and cryptocurrencies showed stronger dependency in turbulent periods, remaining detached in calm times. On this basis, they argued that digital and green assets could serve as hedges against each other.

Another strand of literature focuses on the energy consumption of cryptocurrencies ([Gallersdörfer et al., 2020](#); [Selmi et al., 2022](#)). The proof-of-work mechanism used for cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin or Ethereum, absorbs enormous amounts of energy, increasing the annual electricity consumption and causing considerable environmental damage ([Corbet et al., 2021](#)). Within the safe-haven framework, [Ren and Lucey \(2022\)](#) divides cryptocurrencies into clean and dirty ones based on their energy use. They point out that instruments related to clean energy can act as a safe-haven only for dirty cryptocurrencies. [Sharif et al. \(2023\)](#) analysed the same set of cryptocurrencies and studied the spillover mechanisms between clean and dirty cryptos and green indices representative for the US, European and Asian markets from November 2017 to April 2022. Based on the obtained connectedness network, the authors formulate guidelines for investors looking for safe havens.

[Pham and Do \(2022\)](#) examine the time-varying connectedness between green bonds and implied volatility indices from the stock and bond markets, energy markets, and crucial metals markets. They find that green bonds can act as hedging instruments against uncertainty indices. [Arfaoui et al. \(2023\)](#) analyse the interdependence between clean energy, green markets and cryptocurrencies from January 2018 to the end of November 2021. The authors focus on four cryptos: Bitcoin, Ethereum, Cardano and Ripple. They show that green bonds provide the best diversification possibilities from all analysed assets. [Milunovich \(2022\)](#) assess the connectedness between PoW versus PoS or other digital coins, finding that the former exports more risk, transferring more shocks to other cryptocurrencies in the network than PoS. The level of risk obtained from the financial system is similar for both PoW and PoS. [Sohag et al. \(2023\)](#) investigates if green bonds or green equity are hedges for oil companies' returns, considered dirty assets. They find that oil companies transmit negative volatility spillovers to green investments but receive positive volatility spillovers from them.

The impact of power usage is considered from different perspectives ([Ante et al., 2021](#)). [Karmakar et al. \(2021\)](#) study Bitcoin mining activity versus the volatility changes in the power market, while [De Vries \(2020\)](#) show that miners might undertake suboptimal decisions concerning energy usage. He proposes an approach that allows the evaluation of the methods for obtaining information on Bitcoin's energy demand. [Jabłczyńska et al. \(2023\)](#) confirm these results, demonstrating the ineffectiveness of Bitcoin mining. [Corbet et al. \(2021\)](#) find that the use of power by cryptocurrencies affects the performance of companies in the energy sector. Moreover, [De Vries \(2023\)](#) deliberates on Ethereum, which conducted the transfer from PoW toward PoS, being a potential exemplar for other cryptocurrencies. [Husain et al. \(2023\)](#) ask whether green cryptos are indeed green. The authors demonstrate that green cryptos can be successfully used as diversifiers but not safe-havens. Specifically, investors should use gold or green bonds to protect their investments during market turmoils. Moreover, green and dirty cryptos show a high degree of co-movement.

3 Data

In our analysis, we consider five proof-of-work and five proof-of-stake cryptocurrencies (Ren and Lucey, 2022). The first group, which is referred to throughout the article as dirty or conventional, includes Bitcoin (BTC), Ethereum (ETH), Bitcoin Cash (BCH), Ethereum Classic (ETC) and Litecoin (LTC). The second, named clean or green, consists of Cardano (ADA), Ripple (XRP), IOTA (IOT), Stellar (XLM) and Nano (XNO). In this paper, we classify Ethereum as a dirty cryptocurrency – since only on the 15th of September 2022, this coin started the transferring process from PoW to PoS⁴. This process called *The Merge* was said to reduce Ethereum’s energy consumption by 99.95%. Similarly to Ren and Lucey (2022), we treat ETH as a dirty coin.

As an approximation of dirty energy, we utilize Brent oil futures prices. The data are from the nasdaq.com database. The CELS index approximates the clean energy sector - a modified market capitalization-weighted index that tracks the performance of various companies within clean-energy technologies, including manufacturers, developers, distributors, and installers⁵.

The sample data starts on 15th January 2019 and ends on 15th September 2022. In Figures 1 and 2, we present the log prices of "dirty" and "clean" cryptocurrencies, respectively. In the case of the dirty coins, the whole sample could be divided into two parts: the upward trend from 2019 to mid-2021 and the downward trend from mid-2021 till the end of the sample in September 2022. For clean coins, we observe a shift in the dynamics starting from 2021 - prices increase rapidly till May 2021 and then revert to reaching the same level as at the beginning of 2021 at the end of the sample. In both cases, for dirty and clean coins, the behaviour of prices within a group is similar and different across groups. Figure 3 displays the log prices of Brent oil futures and the log prices of the green energy index, CELS. Both series experienced a decline in March 2020, with a more severe fall affecting oil than clean energy assets and prices of the former taking longer to recover.

In Table 1, we present the descriptive statistics of the log-returns of cryptocurrencies, Brent as a dirty source of energy, and the clean energy index. Among conventional cryptocurrencies (PoW), Ethereum Classic had the highest standard deviation and Bitcoin the lowest. Among green cryptocurrencies, Nano was the most volatile, while the volatility of the other cryptocurrencies was comparable. Both energy sources, dirty and clean, had lower volatility.

4 Methods

In order to verify if the environmental aspects play a role in the decision-making process, we apply the following portfolio construction strategy. We compose a portfolio consisting of one cryptocurrency and Brent/CELS each time. Next, we estimate the multivariate stochastic volatility models with dynamic conditional correlation (MSV-DCC) for the portfolio’s components. We assess whether the assets can hedge oil price fluctuations based on the estimated correlation. Next, we calculate the optimal weights of Brent (CELS) and the respective cryptos in the investment and assess the effectiveness of each strategy. We verify whether the character of the cryptos (dirty or clean) affects the effectiveness.

⁴<https://ethereum.org/en/upgrades/merge/>

⁵For more information see <https://cleanedge.com/indexes/stock-index/cels>. Initially, we considered several green energy indices similar to those used in Ren and Lucey (2022) or Fuentes and Herrera (2020). These were: NASDAQ Clean Edge Green Energy Index (**CELS**), NASDAQ OMX Fuel Cell (**GRNFUEL**), NASDAQ OMX Renewable Energy Generation (**GRNREG**), WilderHill New Energy Global Innovation Index (**NEX**) and WilderHill Clean Energy Index (**ECO**). However, out of these indices, only the CELS has a counterpart in which investors may invest: the First Trust Nasdaq Clean Edge Green Energy Index Fund, **QCLN**. As such, this index is the only one that is directly investable among those proposed in previous works. For these reasons, we focus on this index in the remainder of this study.

Cryptocurrencies: — BCH — BTC - - - ETC - - - ETH - - - LTC

Figure 1: Logarithmic prices of dirty cryptocurrencies (PoW)

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of log-returns of cryptocurrencies, brent and CELS

	Mean	Std.dev.	Min	Max
Dirty cryptocurrencies:				
BTC Bitcoin	0.195	3.809	-37.170	18.746
LTC Litecoin	0.181	5.238	-36.177	30.829
ETH Ethereum	0.296	4.889	-42.347	25.948
ETC Ethereum.Classic	0.330	6.218	-39.733	42.258
BTH Bitcoin.Cash	0.140	5.760	-42.956	52.320
Dirty-energy source:				
Brent oil	0.083	2.907	-24.404	21.019
Clean cryptocurrencies:				
XRP	0.159	5.861	-42.334	56.011
XLM Stellar	0.147	5.748	-33.632	74.924
XNO Nano	0.238	7.560	-44.336	110.884
IOTA	0.152	5.921	-41.932	37.603
ADA Cardano	0.340	5.718	-39.568	32.238
Clean-energy index:				
NASDAQ CELS	0.158	2.392	-12.752	14.041

Cryptocurrencies: ADA IOT XLM XNO XRP

Figure 2: Logarithmic prices of clean cryptocurrencies (PoS)

Figure 3: Logarithmic prices of oil and green energy index CELS

4.1 Dynamic conditional correlation from the Bayesian stochastic volatility model

We use the MSV-DCC model proposed by [Yu and Meyer \(2006\)](#) to model the volatility and covariance of Brent and each portfolio. Stochastic volatility models are counterparts of more popular GARCH models, where volatility is modelled as a stochastic latent variable.

We estimate the model using the Bayesian approach proposed by [Yu and Meyer \(2006\)](#), using WinBUGS and R with package R2WinBUGS ([Sturtz et al., 2005](#)). The method uses the Markov-chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) approach, proposed independently by [Shephard \(1993\)](#) and [Doan et al. \(1994\)](#). The MCMC approach overcomes the problem of simulating values from a complicated multivariate distribution. More precisely, one generates a Markov chain with a stationary distribution equal to the target conditional density and then simulates values from this chain ([Yu and Meyer, 2006](#)).

Let us denote by y_t the series of de-meaned log returns of financial instruments

$$\mathbf{y}_t = (\Delta Brent_t, \Delta Y_t)'$$

where $\Delta Brent$ denotes the log-returns of Brent futures, and ΔY - the return of the potential hedge. We assume that this bi-variate vector can be decomposed into ([Yu and Meyer, 2006](#)):

$$\mathbf{y}_t = \mathbf{\Omega}_t \boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t, \tag{1}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}_t = (\epsilon_{1,t}, \epsilon_{2,t})'$, while $\mathbf{\Omega}_t = \text{diag}(\mathbf{h}_t/2) \sim \text{IID}(\mathbf{0}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\epsilon,t})$ and

$$\boldsymbol{\Sigma}_{\epsilon,t} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \rho_t \\ \rho_t & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \tag{2}$$

Then $\mathbf{h}_t = (h_{1,t}, h_{2,t})$ is a vector of the conditional variances of the process and is modelled as ([Yu and Meyer, 2006](#)):

$$\mathbf{h}_t - \boldsymbol{\mu} = \text{diag}(\phi_{11}, \phi_{22})(\mathbf{h}_{t-1} - \boldsymbol{\mu}) + \boldsymbol{\eta}_{t-1}, \tag{3}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\eta}_t = (\eta_{1,t}, \eta_{2,t})' \sim \text{iid}(\mathbf{0}, \text{diag}(\sigma_{\eta_1}^2, \sigma_{\eta_2}^2))$, while $\boldsymbol{\mu} = (\mu_1, \mu_2)'$.

The model assumes that the conditional correlation between the returns (see eq. 2), is time-varying and follows the autoregressive process:

$$q_t - \psi_0 = \psi(q_{t-1} - \psi_0) + \sigma_\rho v_{t-1}, \tag{4}$$

while $v_t \sim \text{iid}(0, 1)$ and σ_ρ is the variance of the error term in the correlation equation. Furthermore, $\mathbf{h}_0 = \boldsymbol{\mu}$ and $q_0 = \psi_0$.

Eventually, since the correlation should take values from -1 to 1, it is re-scaled accordingly: ([Yu and Meyer, 2006](#)):

$$\rho_t = \frac{\exp(q_t) - 1}{\exp(q_t) + 1}, \tag{5}$$

The Bayesian estimation results rely not only on data but also on the prior distribution, which reflects the modeller's prior knowledge. Thus, following ([Yu and Meyer, 2006](#)), we apply

the priors specified below:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_1 &\sim N(0, 25) \\
\mu_2 &\sim N(0, 25) \\
\phi_{11}^* &\sim \text{Beta}(20, 1.5), \text{ where } \phi_{11}^* = \frac{1}{2}(\phi_{11} + 1) \\
\phi_{22}^* &\sim \text{Beta}(20, 1.5), \text{ where } \phi_{22}^* = \frac{1}{2}(\phi_{22} + 1) \\
\sigma_{\eta_1}^2 &\sim \text{Inverse - Gamma}(2.5, 0.025) \\
\sigma_{\eta_2}^2 &\sim \text{Inverse - Gamma}(2.5, 0.025) \\
\psi^* &\sim \text{Beta}(20, 1.5), \text{ where } \psi^* = \frac{1}{2}(\psi + 1) \\
\psi_0 &\sim N(0.7, 10) \\
\sigma_\rho^2 &\sim \text{Inverse - Gamma}(2.5, 0.025)
\end{aligned}$$

4.2 Hedging ratios

To answer the question of whether cryptocurrencies can effectively hedge the price movements of oil, we follow [Kroner and Sultan \(1993\)](#) and calculate the optimal and time-varying weights of cryptocurrencies in a portfolio consisting of oil/CEGE and each of the cryptocurrencies according to the following formula:

$$w_{cr} = \frac{h_{oil/CEGE} - h_{oil/CEGE,cr}}{h_{cr} + h_{oil/CEGE} - 2 \cdot h_{cr}} \quad (6)$$

where $h_{oil/CEGE}$ and h_{cr} are the conditional variances of the returns of oil/CEGE and cryptocurrencies (cr), respectively, from the bivariate SV-MGARCH models, and $h_{oil/CEGE,cr}$ is the conditional covariance of the returns of oil/CEGE and a given cryptocurrency. For clarity, we omit here the time-index t , but we note that the variance and co-variance used in the equation are conditional ones, and, hence, time-varying. We assume that the weights in the optimal portfolio are non-negative:

$$w_{cr} = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } w_{cr} < 0 \\ w_{cr} & \text{if } 0 \leq w_{cr} \leq 1 \\ 1 & \text{if } w_{cr} > 1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The assessment of the performance of the hedging portfolio is done based on the hedging effectiveness ratio, HE_t , defined as:

$$HE_t = \frac{var_{unhedged,t} - var_{hedged,t}}{var_{unhedged,t}} \quad (8)$$

where $var_{unhedged}$ denotes the variance of returns of the unhedged portfolio, which consists of one instrument – the Brent oil, while var_{hedged} is the variance of a portfolio, which consists of both oil/CELS and cryptocurrency. Using the Bayesian approach we are able to obtain the 95% interval for the hedge effectiveness and determine in which case the effectiveness is significantly different from 0.

5 Empirical results

The stochastic volatility (SV) approach allows us to obtain the confidence intervals for the estimates of the correlations. In Figures 4 and 6, we present the correlation between Brent and cryptocurrencies, while in Figures 5 and 7 - between green energy approximated by CELS index and cryptocurrencies. Each figure shows the 95% confidence interval of conditional correlation. If the interval covers zero, we assume that the correlation was insignificant. Such a situation implies the presence of hedging opportunities.

Based on the graphs mentioned above, we indicate that among the hedging opportunities for investment in Brent, we can consider Stellar and XRP from the set of clean cryptocurrencies and Bitcoin Cash and Litecoin from the dirty cryptocurrencies. Regarding clean energy, approximated by the CELS index, we found no such cryptocurrency that was insignificantly correlated with the base instrument during the whole analysis period. In each case, the correlation was positive since the second half of 2021 or the beginning of 2022. Neither clean nor dirty cryptocurrencies can be considered a constant hedge against the CELS index.

(a) Brent vs Cardano

(b) Brent vs IOTA

(c) Brent vs Nano

(d) Brent vs Stellar

(e) Brent vs XRP

Figure 4: Conditional correlation between the clean cryptocurrencies and Brent – 95% confidence intervals

In the next step, we examine the effectiveness of crypto-hedge against Brent. Therefore, we calculate the confidence intervals for hedging ratios for portfolios consisting of Brent and dirty or clean coins. In Figures 12-13, we present the comparison of the volatilities of Brent and clean and dirty cryptocurrencies. We observe that although the cryptocurrencies were much less correlated with Brent, their high volatility makes such a hedge less profitable than one of the clean energy indices.

In Figure 8 and 9, we present the confidence interval of hedge effectiveness calculated for the 2.5% and 97.5% quantiles of volatility and correlation estimates. When the lower bound

(a) CELS vs Cardano

(b) CELS vs IOTA

(c) CELS vs Nano

(d) CELS vs Stellar

(e) CELS vs XRP

Figure 5: Conditional correlation between the CELS index and clean cryptos - the 95% confidence intervals

(a) Brent vs Bitcoin Cash

(b) Brent vs Bitcoin

(c) Brent vs Ethereum Classic

(d) Brent vs Ethereum

(e) Brent vs Litecoin

Figure 6: Conditional correlation between the Brent crude oil and dirty cryptocurrencies - the 95% confidence intervals

(a) CELS vs Bitcoin Cash

(b) CELS vs Bitcoin

(c) CELS vs Ethereum Classic

(d) CELS vs Ethereum

(e) CELS vs Litecoin

Figure 7: Conditional correlation between the CELS index and dirty cryptos - the 95% confidence intervals

Figure 8: Estimated hedge effectiveness of clean cryptocurrencies against Brent crude oil

of such interval equals zero, we conclude that the hedge was ineffective despite the high value of the upper bound. Cryptocurrencies - clean and dirty - only provided significant protection during periods of oil market turmoil, i.e. in early 2020, when oil prices fell dramatically due to the global ban on mobility.

In the next step, we focus on the effectiveness of crypto-hedge against green energy. In figures 10 and 11, we present the respective plots for clean energy and dirty/clean cryptocurrencies. The effectiveness of the crypto-hedge was most often insignificant (i.e. the hedge was ineffective). We notice only brief periods of non-zero performance for each cryptocurrency for several weeks - in the case of Cardano, IOTA, and Nano, these fall at the start of the pandemic and towards the end of 2020. In the case of Stellar, the highest efficiency was achieved in the second quarter of 2021, coinciding with the cryptocurrency's most intense price growth period. For XRP, these periods of non-zero effectiveness are the longest and cover mainly the beginning of the COVID period.

Finally, we compare the effectiveness of crypto-hedge against dirty and clean energy. Table 2 shows the summary statistics of the hedging effectiveness of each crypto against both types of assets. We find that, regarding the reduction of variance, cryptocurrencies offer better

(a) Bitcoin Cash

(b) Bitcoin

(c) Ethereum Classic

(d) Ethereum

(e) Litecoin

Figure 9: Estimated hedge effectiveness of dirty cryptocurrencies against Brent crude oil

(a) Cardano

(b) IOTA

(c) Nano

(d) Stellar

(e) XRP

Figure 10: Estimated hedge effectiveness of clean cryptos against green energy approximated by CELS

(a) Bitcoin Cash

(b) Bitcoin

(c) Ethereum Classic

(d) Ethereum

(e) Litecoin

Figure 11: Estimated hedge effectiveness of dirty cryptos against green energy approximated by CELS

protection against dirty energy volatility than against the volatility of clean energy. Within the dirty cryptocurrencies group, the mean effectiveness of the hedge against Brent was the highest for Bitcoin (0.28), Ethereum Classic (0.21) and Bitcoin Cash (0.2). Within the clean cryptocurrencies, the leaders were XRP (0.26) and Stellar (0.22).

We obtain a similar rank of hedges for clean energy. Bitcoin and XRP were the most effective (with mean effectiveness equal to 0.18 and 0.14, respectively), Ethereum Classic took the third place (0.12), followed by Stellar (0.11) and Bitcoin Cash (0.10). We note, however, that the variability of the most effective hedges (measured with standard deviation) was also the highest.

To summarise, the effectiveness of the crypto-hedge against clean and dirty energy did not depend on the cryptocurrency’s protocol. The effectiveness of the best clean-crypto hedge was close to the effectiveness of the best dirty-crypto (which partially confirms the results of [Husain et al. \(2023\)](#)). Thus, environmentally aware investors could utilize the green cryptos as hedges against both types of energy assets equally effectively.

Table 2: Summary statistics of hedging effectiveness

	Min	Mean	Max	SD	Min	Mean	Max	SD
	BRENT				CELS			
Clean cryptos:								
Cardano	0.000	0.123	0.760	0.156	0.000	0.057	0.472	0.081
IOTA	0.000	0.174	0.861	0.174	0.000	0.058	0.462	0.075
Nano	0.000	0.187	0.872	0.180	0.000	0.081	0.556	0.107
Stellar	0.000	0.217	0.829	0.199	0.000	0.114	0.681	0.134
XRP	0.000	0.256	0.921	0.240	0.000	0.144	0.765	0.171
Dirty cryptos:								
Bitcoin.Cash	0.000	0.203	0.875	0.198	0.000	0.097	0.724	0.137
Bitcoin	0.000	0.279	0.900	0.216	0.000	0.178	0.826	0.178
Ethereum.Classic	0.000	0.208	0.877	0.202	0.000	0.123	0.754	0.157
Ethereum	0.000	0.164	0.833	0.178	0.000	0.090	0.579	0.115
Litecoin	0.000	0.186	0.870	0.198	0.000	0.093	0.586	0.119

6 Conclusions and policy implications

This study aimed to test whether cryptocurrencies, which differ in their proofing mechanisms and associated energy consumption, have similar hedging properties. Based on their proofing mechanism, we considered so-called dirty and clean cryptocurrencies and built portfolios in which we combined cryptocurrencies with instruments representing dirty or clean energy sources. We examined whether the effectiveness of crypto-hedge differs for clean assets and dirty energy.

Concerning hedging ability, we observe that correlations between cryptocurrencies and dirty energy source, Brent, differ from those between cryptocurrencies and clean energy source, CELS. In the first case, we can find cryptocurrencies insignificantly correlated with Brent for the whole period analysed. Such assets have the potential to hedge portfolios regularly. That was not the case for CELS - the correlations became positive and grew, regardless of the cryptocurrency. Therefore, cryptocurrencies appeared more suitable for securing dirty energy than clean one.

We also considered the effectiveness of the hedge, which takes into account not only correlations but also volatility. The effectiveness of the cryptocurrency as a hedge did not depend on the proofing mechanism, and it was equally good for Bitcoin, which is a dirty coin, as it was for XRP, a clean coin. We found that the effectiveness of crypto-hedge was higher for Brent than

for CELS. The dynamic analysis of hedging effectiveness shows that the respective portfolios should be rebalanced often.

Our results show that all considered assets, clean and dirty coins, could serve as hedges for both energy sources. Thus, the investors can choose clean assets to protect their investment - either in clean or dirty energy - and retain the same effectiveness. That result is especially important from an environmentally-oriented point of view. It denotes that the ecologically burdensome protection can be replaced by an eco-friendly counterpart. However, it should be borne in mind that such a portfolio will require frequent rebalancing to ensure the effectiveness of the hedge.

Both academia and industry seem to regard environmental risks as an obstacle to long-term development. More and more countries recognise the importance of reducing carbon footprint and associated costs through regulations. The growing importance of energy consumption used in the approval process for cryptocurrencies is reflected in the emerging awareness of investors, as indicated by the values of the Cryptocurrency Environmental Attention Index, ICEA, proposed by Wang et al. (2022). Regulators should not only take care of the issues related to cryptocurrency trading, transparency, disclosure, authorisation or supervision as in Markets in Crypto-Assets Regulation (MiCA)⁶, but also the consequences of uncontrolled coin mining in a way that is harmful to the environment. The change in Ethereum's proofing systems demonstrates that reducing environmental costs is possible and well-received in the investment community.

Future work should aim to disentangle whether the change of the Ethereum protocol from proof-of-work to proof-of-stake has changed its characteristics, concerning diversification and hedge possibilities. It would also be necessary to expand the dirty energy asset mix to include other benchmarks such as WTI, as well as other asset classes such as gas or fuel oil.

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⁶<https://www.esma.europa.eu/esmas-activities/digital-finance-and-innovation/markets-crypto-assets-regulation-mica>

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(a) Cardano

(b) IOTA

(c) Nano

(d) Stellar

(e) XRP

Figure 12: Comparison of Brent volatility with clean cryptos

8 Appendix

8.1 Volatility reduction - investment in Brent and cryptocurrencies

8.2 Volatility reduction - investment in Brent and CELS

(a) Bitcoin Cash

(b) Bitcoin

(c) Ethereum Classic

(d) Ethereum

(e) Litecoin

Figure 13: Comparison of Brent volatility with dirty cryptos

(a) Cardano

(b) IOTA

(c) Nano

(d) Stellar

(e) XRP

Figure 14: Comparison of green energy (CELS) volatility with clean cryptos

(a) Bitcoin Cash

(b) Bitcoin

(c) Ethereum Classic

(d) Ethereum

(e) Litecoin

Figure 15: Comparison of CELS volatility with dirty cryptos